

Studies on 3-Oxo-Glutaric Acid Dianilide.

Part—I : Acid-Base Properties

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THE fact that several di- and tri-keto compounds (their enol forms) have wide application in analytical chemistry has created renewed interest in their analytical properties such as acid-base properties, and behaviour as metallochromic indicators with the emphasis on specificity or selectivity, stoichiometry and sensitivity.

A number of these compounds^{1,2} have been thoroughly investigated, their absorption spectra recorded and the stability constants and composition of some of their metal complexes established. The acid-base properties and keto-enol equilibria of some β -di- and tri-keto compounds were studied by several investigators, using pH-metric^{3,4}, spectrophotometric^{5,6}, nmr^{7,8} and polarographic^{9,10} methods.

The present work aims to throw light on the phenomena and processes taking place as the acidity of acetone dicarboxylic acid dianilide and its chloride and methyl derivatives [ADDA (I), *p*-Cl-ADDA (II) and *p*-CH₃-ADDA (III), respectively] is changed, depending on the substituted group. In order to investigate the acid-base properties of compounds I, II and III, titrations of their dilute solutions against standard sodium hydroxide solution were carried out potentiometrically. From the plot of $\log [\text{salt}]/[\text{acid}]$ vs pH (Fig. 1), the pK values of the hydroxyl groups of the enol forms were determined. The absorption spectra of compounds I, II and III were studied in the uv region at various pH values to determine the ionization constants of their weaker hydroxyl groups and to confirm the pH-measurements.

Experimental

Reagents and equipments: All reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Dianilides (I, II, III): The tri-ketoanilides under investigation were prepared by heating ethyl acetone dicarboxylate (1 mole) with amine (2 moles) in 30 ml pyridine for 4 hr. The crude products were crystallized twice from ethanol in 80% yield¹¹. The 10^{-3} M solutions of dianilides (I, II, III) were prepared by dissolving the required amount of these compounds in known volumes of ethanol and dilute solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution, using the same solvent. Ethanol-water

Fig. 1. (a) *p*-CH₃-ADDA; (b) *p*-Cl-ADDA; (c) ADDA.

(1 : 1) solutions were used for studying the absorption spectra.

A Beckman pH-meter H-2 model G 8509 with T-2 titration attachment was used for recording the pH and a PYE Unicam UV spectrophotometer, Model 1750, with 1 cm quartz cells was used for recording the absorbance at different pH values. The titration cell consisted of a 100 ml beaker, a microburette and calomel electrodes. 0.01 M solution of NaOH (carbonate free) was used for titration and 0.01 N solution of Na₂CO₃ and 0.01 N solution of HCl were used for adjusting the pH. The water used was twice distilled from all glass equipments.

pH-metric titration: 5 ml of 0.01 M solution of ADDA or one of its two derivatives, *p*-Cl-ADDA and *p*-CH₃-ADDA, was taken in the titration cell and 50 ml of alcohol-water mixture (1 : 1) was added. The mixed solution was titrated with 0.01 M sodium hydroxide solution, keeping the tip of the burette immersed in the solution. The pH of the solution was recorded after each addition of alkali.

Absorbance measurements: 8×10^{-5} M solutions of ADDA or *p*-Cl-ADDA and 5×10^{-5} M solution of *p*-CH₃-ADDA were prepared by dilution of the respective stock and 10 ml portion of each was taken, pH adjusted to the required value with Na₂CO₃ or HCl solution and absorbances in the region 210 to 350 nm were recorded. Alcohol-water mixture (1 : 1) was used as blank. pH of the solutions were also checked immediately after each set of measurements.

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Results and Discussion

The results obtained in the titration of 5 ml 10^{-2} M ADDA (I), *p*-Cl-ADDA (II) or *p*-CH₃-ADDA (III) against 0.01 M NaOH indicate that the extent of ionization increases in the order of *p*-CH₃-ADDA, ADDA, *p*-Cl-ADDA. The calculated *pK* values, at the intersection of the straight line of the plot of $\log [\text{salt}]/[\text{acid}]$ vs *pH* (Fig. 1 a, b and c), amount to 9.90, 9.35, 9.25.

A typical absorption spectrum of the compound (III) (Fig. 2) in solutions of different *pH* values from 1.4 to 7.0 is characterized by a sharp band at 250 nm which is due to a $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the conjugate system of the molecules (i, ii, iii), as given by the equilibria,

The fact that the absorption spectra is unchanged over the *pH* range 1.4 to 7.0 confirms high *pK* values of the enol form (i). The increase of *pH* from 7.0 to 12.0 results in a hypochromic effect and a subsequent decrease in *E* from 28400 to 19000 for the primary band at 250 nm. Ascending band appears at 300 nm in case of I and III and at 310 nm in case of II. The intensity of this band increases with the increase of *pH* reaching the limiting value with *E* of 20500 at *pH* 12, which may be assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the forms (ii and iii).

The first decrease in absorbance at 250 nm is attributed to the ionization of OH of the enol forms (i and ii) of the anilide carbonyl groups. This is substantiated by the fact that the ionization of the OH groups which are not involved in a hydrogen bond, requires a lower energy^{2,3}. Also the tautomerism favouring the participation of the

anilide carbonyl in hydrogen bonding in structure (i) may retard the ionization of the OH of the enol form of the acetone carbonyl which is confirmed by increase in absorbance at 300-310 nm within the *pH* range 7-12. These results are in good agreement with these obtained by *pH* measurements.

The presence of some isobestic points in the absorption spectra is an indication of the equilibria existing previously (i, ii and iii).

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of 5×10^{-6} M *p*-CH₃-ADDA in solutions of varying *pH* values.

The variation of absorbance with *pH* is used for calculating *pK* values using recommended procedure^{2,3}. These values differed within ± 0.1 from the *pH*-metric data. Therefore, both *pH*-metric and spectrophotometric data indicate that *p*-Cl helps and *p*-CH₃ decreases the ionization of the parent ADDA. This becomes more clear by the calculation of the standard free energy changes from the ionization constants of the given compounds (Table 1).

Compound	X or R	<i>pK</i>	ΔG° Kcal mol ⁻¹
I	H	9.35	12.893
II	Cl	9.25	12.696
III	CH ₃	9.90	13.588

The difference between ΔG° of *p*-Cl-ADDA and that of ADDA is equal to -0.137 Kcal mol⁻¹ and means that Cl helps ionization of enol form of *p*-Cl-ADDA, whereas the difference between free

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energy change of ADDA and *p*-CH₃-ADDA is equal to + 0.755 Kcal mol⁻¹ indicating that CH₃ group decreases the tendency of ionization of the enol form of ADDA.

These results are in good agreement with the fact¹⁴ that the electron withdrawing abilities of the ring substituents in anilides is known to be -OCH₃ < -CH₃ < -H < -Cl and would lead to the conclusion that this would be the order of the values of acid dissociation constants of the enol forms of the compounds I, II and III as indicated in Table I.

References

1. M. A. ZAYED and M. M. S. EL-MORSY, *Egyptian J. Chem.*, 1980, 23, 1.
2. M. A. ZAYED and M. M. S. EL-MORSY, *Egyptian J. Chem.*, communicated.

3. J. KROUPA, *Chem. Prum.*, 1973, 23, 244.
4. L. HEVESI, P. VAN BRANDT and A. BRUYLANT, *Bull. Soc. Chem. France*, II, 1970, 3971.
5. A. D. TANEJA and K. P. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 95.
6. L. HEVESI and A. BRUYLANT, *Bull. Soc. Chem. France*, II, 1971, 4066.
7. J. L. BURDETT and M. T. ROGERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 2105.
8. M. REGITZ and H. J. GRELHEAR, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1969, 108.
9. G. NISLI, D. BARNE and O. ZUMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 64.
10. A. S. SHAWALI, B. E. ALANADOULI and M. H. SAMMOUR, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1976, 21, 881.
11. M. M. S. EL-MORSY, "Reactions with Acetone Dicarboxylic Dianilides", Ph.D. Thesis, Cairo University, 1974.
12. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA, M. R. MAHMOUD and Y. M. TOMORIK, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, 253, 289.
13. R. M. ISSA and A. H. ZOWAIL, *J. Chem. A. R. E.*, 1971, 14, 461.
14. H. J. HARRIES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, 25, 519.